

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

EXTRACTION AND PHOTOMETRIC INVESTIGATION OF CHROMIUM (VI) COMPLEXES WITH 2-HYDROXY-5-CHLOROTHIOPHENOL AND HYDROPHOBIC AMINES

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Abstract

Upon interaction of chromium (VI) ion with 2-hydroxy-5-chlorothiophenol, complex compounds with various ligands are formed and extracted with chloroform. O-tolidine (o-tol) and m-tolidine (m-tol) were used as hydrophobic amines. The optimum conditions for extraction and photometric determination of chromium were determined. The pH of the aqueous phase was 0.2-7.3 and 2.2-5.3 for the formation and maximum extraction of complexes with various ligands. Their composition and structure were studied by IR and NMR spectroscopy using physicochemical methods.

Chromium complexes absorb light at wavelengths of 437-528 nm, respectively. The molar coefficient of light absorption of chromium complexes is (2.69-5.3)-104. Chromium (III) is 98.2-99.8% extracted with chloroform as a multi-ligand complex (MLC). The molar ratio of components in the complexes was determined by several methods, their ratio was Cr(III):HHTF:AM 1:3:3:3. It was confirmed that during complex formation Cr(VI) is reduced to Cr(III) by 2-hydroxy-5-chlorothiophenol.

Complexes with different ligands do not polymerize in the organic phase and are in monomeric form ($\gamma=0.98-1.12$). The developed new methodology was applied for the determination of chromium in soil, various grades of steel, drinking and ground waters, plants, milk, and dairy products.

Keywords: chromium, 2-hydroxy-5-chlorothiophenol, extraction, aminophenols, external ions, spectrophotometry.

Introduction

In recent years, interest in the analytical chemistry of chromium has increased dramatically. This is due to various applications of chromium and its compounds. Recently, MLC with mixed coordination sphere, which has better characteristics than single-ligand complexes, has been used in the practice of analytical chemistry. In this connection, MLC has found a wide range of applications in analytical chemistry and chemical technology [1-4, 6, 7].

Purpose

Standard solution with a concentration of Cr(VI) which is equal to 1 mg/ml was prepared by dissolving K₂Cr₂O₇ salt in 1000 ml of distilled water. Standardization of the solution was carried out titrimetrically using diphenylamine. The ionic strength ($\mu=0.1$) was kept constant by adding calculated amounts of KCl, NaCl, and NaNO₃ to the solution. 0.1 M HCl, NaOH, KOH and different types of buffer solutions were used to create an optimum pH.

Methodology of work

Different amounts (10-100 μ g) of chromium (VI) solution are poured into the separating funnels and 2.8 ml of 0.01 M HXTPH and 1.2 ml of 0.1 M AF solution are added. After establishing optimum acidity using 2 mL of 0.1 M HCl solution, stir vigorously for 1 minute. The organic phase is separated from the aqueous phase

and after waiting for 15 min its optical density is measured on a photocolorimeter KFK-2 or spectrophotometer SF-26 in a bath of thickness $l=0.5$ cm.

Reduction of chromium (VI) ion to chromium (III) ion.

1,5-diphenylcarbazide (DPC) reacts with Cr (VI) in an acidic medium to form a purple-colored compound. Cr(VI) was found to oxidize diphenylcarbazide to diphenylcarbazone.

Does diphenylcarbazide change valence when chromium(VI) interacts with HHTPh accordingly? Two series of experiments were carried out to find out: 1) Cr(VI) ions were reduced to Cr(III) using SnCl₂ or KJ in a hydrochloric acid medium. 2) This reaction was carried out without the use of additional reducing agents. In both cases, the brightness of the solutions was the same. Consequently, Cr(VI) ions are reduced to Cr(III) by the reagent itself in the process of complexation [5].

Based on the obtained results, a graded curve is plotted. Compliance with Bera's law is observed in the range of chromium concentrations 0.5-16 μ g/ml. When chromium (III) interacts with HYTPH, a light brown colored complex insoluble in non-polar organic solvents is formed. The anionic complex is formed over a wide pH range (1.8-7.0). When added to the AF system, the anionic complex passes into the organic phase as a multiligand ion-associate complex (IAC).

Extractant choice.

In extractive-photometric analysis, the correct choice of a suitable solvent is the main condition for selective and quantitative separation of metal ions. $[\text{MeR}_2]_2$ - MLC Am type different classes of organic solvents - alcohols (butyl, amyl), aromatic hydrocarbons (benzene, toluene, xylene), simple esters (isoamyl acetate, ethyl benzoate), halogen derivatives of hydrocarbons (chlorobenzene, chloroform, 1, 2- can be extracted with dichloroethane). Chloroform, dichloroethane, and chlorobenzene are recognized as the best extractants. When chloroform is used as an extractant,

an equilibrium is established and the maximum degree of extraction (R) of Cr(III) ions in the form of complexes with various ligands is equal to 98.4-98.8%.

pH dependence of the aqueous phase.

The pH of the aqueous phase should be 0.2-7.3 for the formation and extraction of chromium MLCs, and 2.2-5.3 for maximum extraction. As can be seen from Figure 1, the extraction of chromium (III) in the form of MLC increases with increasing pH. With further increase in pH, the extraction rate decreases due to the inability of the Am molecule to protonate and hydrolysis of the ionic form of chromium forming the complex.

Figure 1. Dependence of luminescence of chromium (VI) MLC with HHTF and Am on pH of the aqueous phase
a) 1-Cr(III)-HXTPh-p-Tol, 2-Cr(III)-HXTPh-m-Tol, 3-Cr(III)-HXTPh-o-Tol, 4-Cr(III)-HBTF-p-Tol, 5-Cr(III)-HBTF-m-Tol, 6-Cr(III)-HBTF-o-Tol
b) 1-Cr(III)-HBTF-AF₁, 2-Cr(III)-HBTF-AF₂

$C_{\text{Cr}} = 3.84 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $C_{\text{HHTF}} = (1.0-1.4) \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $C_{\text{Am}} = (1.12 - 1.16) \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, KFK-2, $\lambda = 490 \text{ nm}$, $\ell = 0.5 \text{ cm}$.

Electronic spectrum of the complexes.

Chloroform extracts of Cr(III)-HHTF-AM complexes absorb a maximum of light at 437-528 nm. A

bathochromic shift of 152-320 nm is observed during the formation of MLC (Fig. 2.a)

Figure 2. Absorption spectra of chloroform extracts of MLCs formed by chromium (III) with HHTPh and Am.
a) 1-Cr(III)-HXTPh-p-Tol, 2-Cr(III)-HXTPh-m-Tol, 3-Cr(III)-HXTPh-o-Tol, 4-Cr(III)-HBTF-p-Tol, 5-Cr(III)-HBTF-m-Tol, 6-Cr(III)-HBTF-o-Tol
b) 1-Cr(III)-HXTPh-AF₁, 2-Cr(III)-HBTF-AF₂

$C_{\text{Cr(III)}} = 3.84 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $C_{\text{HHTF}} = (1.0-1.4) \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $C_{\text{Am}} = (1.12 - 1.16) \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, SF-26, $\ell = 1.0 \text{ cm}$.

The composition of the components of the complexes with different ligands was determined by the

equilibrium shift, straight-line, and relative yield Asm methods. The results of the determination are presented in (Fig. 3). By Nazarenko's method it was found

that the molar ratio of components in MLC is Cr(III):HHTPh: Am=1:3:3:3.

In the HXTPh molecule, the SH valence vibrations (2600-2550 cm⁻¹) and the broad intense absorption band observed in the interval 3600-3200 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the maximum VSH=2580 cm⁻¹ are completely lost in the IR spectrum of the HXTPh molecule of MLC. In the formation of chromium complexes with HXTPh and hydrophobic amines by the Nazarenko method, it was found that one proton from each molecular ligand is substituted by chromium. MLCs do not

polymerize in the organic phase but exist as monomers. It varies in the interval (γ=0.98-1.12). The conditional stability constant of MLC is lgβ_{k.d}=6.62-10.73. The extraction constant of MLC in the [Cr(HR)₃]-AmH⁺-H₂O-CHCl₃ system is lgK_{ek}=6.62-10.73. The equilibrium constant is lgK_t=2.37-9.31.

The metrological characteristics of the technique were established. The amount of the component in the sample determined by the result of a single measurement cannot be accurately determined. To obtain accurate results, 5 parallel experiments were carried out.

Table 1

Statistical characterization of the method for the extraction-spectrophotometric determination of chromium (III) with HXTPh and Am (n=5, P=0.95)

Cr(III)-HHTPh-Am	Chromium(III) extracted, μg/ml	S	S _χ	S _r	$\bar{X} \pm \frac{t_{p,f} S}{\sqrt{n}}$ mkq/ml
Cr(III)-HXTPh-An	0.2	0.014	0.007	0.038	0.202 ± 0.018
	0.4	0.016	0.008	0.045	0.399 ± 0.019
	0.6	0.022	0.014	0.037	0.605 ± 0.022
	0.8	0.043	0.024	0.031	0.795 ± 0.027
	1.2	0.079	0.051	0.042	1.203 ± 0.059
Cr(III)-HXTPh-mAn	0.1	0.015	0.004	0.031	0.099 ± 0.012
	0.3	0.017	0.008	0.024	0.308 ± 0.017
	0.6	0.022	0.013	0.036	0.600 ± 0.025
	0.9	0.045	0.019	0.038	0.905 ± 0.034
	1.2	0.079	0.048	0.040	1.206 ± 0.038

Based on the results obtained, standard deviations and relative standard deviations are found. The table shows that the newly developed methods are quite accurate and reliable.

To find out the influence of the MLC continuity on the determination limit, the rank plot coefficients were determined by the least squares method.

$$\sum A = a \sum c + nb$$

$$\sum Ac = a \sum c^2 + b \sum c$$

The range of Burr's law compliance (0.2-24 μg/ml) and other parameters are given in Table 2.

Table 2

Analytical performance of methods for the determination of chromium (III) HXTPh and MLC with Am

Chromium(III) MLC	Conditions for drawing a graded curve			Compliance with Bera's law (μg/ml)	Graduated curve equation	Minimum limit of detection (μg/ml)
	pH _{opt}	M, C _{HHTF} × 10 ⁻³	M, C _{Am} × 10 ⁻³			
Cr-HXTPh- <i>o</i> -kyslidyne	4,3-6,4.	1.12	0.20	0,4-20	0.02+0.014x	0.065
Cr-HXTPh- <i>m</i> -kyslidyne	4,3-6,4.	1.00	0.24	0,4-22	0.018+0.026x	0.043
Cr-HXTPh- <i>p</i> -kyslidyne	4,3-6,4.	0.95	0.30	0,4-24	0.031+0.019x	0.055
Cr-HXTPh-An	3.1-4.5	0.95	0.27	0.5-14	0.014 + 0.0093x	0.012
Cr-HXTPh-mAniline	3.2-4.7	0.88	0.35	0.5-14	0.013 + 0.0098 x	0.011
Cr-HXTPh-dAniline	3.4-4.9	0.94	0.38	0.5-16	0.015 + 0.0106x	0.010
Cr-HXTPh- AF ₁	2.5-4.1	1.09	0.70	0.2-18	0.025+0.024x	0.037
Cr-HXTPh- AF ₂	2.2-3.9	1.01	0.78	0.2-19	0.019+0.073x	0.081
Cr-HXTPh-AF ₃	2.5-5.7	1.08	0.25	0.5-16	0.035+0.027x	0.045
Cr-HXTPh-AF ₄	2.5-5.7	1.08	0.25	0.5-18	0.029+0.026x	0.031
Cr-HXTPh-AF ₅	2.5-5.7	1.08	0.25	0.5-16	0.017+0.023x	0.048

The barrier effect of foreign ions.

The large amount of alkaline, alkaline earth, and

rare earth elements does not interfere with the determination of these cations. The interference of

external ions was overcome by changing pH, using absorbers, and extraction. From preliminary experiments, it was known that Fe(III), Hg(II), Cu(II), and Ti(IV) ions interfered with the determination of chromium. The inhibition of molybdenum and tungsten

was eliminated by adding oxalate ion and citric acid, respectively, to the solution. The results obtained show that chromium can be determined by extraction spectrophotometry in the presence of foreign ions. It is summarised in Table 3.

Table 3

Determination of chromium(III) in the form of MLC with HXTPh and Am (30 mkq chromium is taken, n=3, P=0.95)

Ion	Molar ratio Cr(III):ion	Masking reagent	It has been found Cr, mkq			
			dAn(S _r ·10 ²)	mAn (S _r ·10 ²)	An(S _r ·10 ²)	
Cu(II)	1:35		30.6 (2.3)	30.4 (2.3)	30.0 (1.3)	
Fe(III)	1:80		30.0 (4.2)	39.9 (4.1)	30.2 (3.2)	
Al(III)	1:190		30.5 (1.6)	30.3 (1.5)	30.0 (2.5)	
Bi(III)	1:40		29.5 (3.5)	29.7 (4.4)	29.5 (4.0)	
Mo(VI)	1:15		29.7 (2.4)	29.8 (2.1)	29.5 (2.0)	
Ti(VI)	1:50		29.6 (2.3)	29.8 (2.6)	29.8 (2.1)	
Co(II)	1:100		30.4 (4.2)	30.0 (3.2)	30.4 (2.9)	
Ni(II)	1:100		30.0 (1.5)	30.3 (1.8)	30.2 (1.2)	
Zr(IV)	1:60		29.6 (2.3)	29.8 (2.0)	29.4 (2.7)	
V(IV)	1:10		30.0 (1.5)	30.3 (1.2)	30.5 (1.7)	
W(VI)	1:80		30.5 (4.2)	30.2 (4.1)	30.5 (4.0)	
Nb(V)	1:30		NaF	30.0 (1.5)	30.4 (1.8)	30.6 (2.5)
Ta(V)	1:50		Na ₂ SO ₃	29.6 (2.3)	30.6 (2.9)	29.9 2.6)
Hg(II)	1:35			29.7 (2.4)	29.8 (2.8)	29.6 (3.4)
Na,K	1:1500			30.0 (1.5)	30.1 (3.5)	30.5 (2.1)
Ca	1:800			30.0 (1.5)	30.3 (1.7)	30.2 (4.5)
Mg	1:900			30.0 (1.5)	30.5 (1.8)	30.5 (1.5)
Be	1:700			30.5 (4.2)	30.9 (3.6)	30.2 (4.2)
Zn	1:600			30.0 (1.5)	30.8 (1.8)	30.3 (1.5)
Ba	1:850			30.6 (2.3)	29.5 (3.5)	30.6 (2.3)
Cd	1:500		30.0 (4.2)	29.7 (2.4)	30.0 (4.2)	
Mn(II)	1:43		30.5 (1.6)	29.6 (2.3)	30.5 (1.6)	
Ga(III)	1:540		30.3 (1.8)	30.0 (3.2)	30.0 (3.2)	
Sn(IV)	1:56	Oxalate-ion	29.8 2.0)	30.3 (1.8)	30.3 (1.8)	
Mo(VI)	1:42		30.3 (1.2)	29.8 (2.0)	29.8 (2.0)	
C ₂ O ₄ ²⁻	1:68		30.5 (4.0)	30.0 (2.5)	30.5 (4.0)	
EDTA	1:58		30.6 (2.5)	29.5 (4.0)	30.6 (2.5)	
Urea	1:60		29.9 (2.6)	29.5 (2.0)	29.9 (2.6)	
Thiourea	1:79		29.8 (2.1)	29.4 (2.7)	29.7 (2.4)	
Citric acid	1:40		29.8 (2.6)	30.5 (1.7)	29.6 (2.3)	
Alcali acid	1:700		30.0 (3.2)	30.5 (4.0)	30.0 (3.2)	

Determination of chromium in drinking and ground waters.

The drinking and groundwater were kept for two days, 3.0 ml of solid H₂SO₄ was added and evaporated to a residue of 20 ml. After cooling, the condensed water sample was diluted with distilled water to the line and filtered through filter paper into a 50 ml flask. An aliquot of this solution was taken and chromium was determined as in the construction of the standard curve. The metrological characteristics of the analysis result were calculated. It is given in Table 4.[8]

Table 4

Determination of chromium (III) in drinking water and groundwater (n=5, P=0.95)

Compound	Included, mcg	Found, mcg	$\bar{X} \pm \frac{t_{p,S}}{\sqrt{n}}$, mkq/l	S _r
Drinking water				
Cr(III)-HXTPh- <i>o</i> -Tol	3.0	3.47	3.47±0.045	0.013
Cr(III)-HXTPh- <i>m</i> -Tol	4.3	4.78	4.78±0.018	0.024
Cr(III)-HXTPh- <i>p</i> -Tol	6.2	6.65	6.65±0.029	0.011
Diphenylcarbazine	6.0	6.47	6.47±0.037	0.025
Groundwater				
Cr(III)-HXTPh- <i>o</i> -Tol	3.0	3.60	4.60±0.028	0.029
Diphenylcarbazine	5.4	6.03	6.47±0.041	0.051

Conclusion

2-Hydroxy-5-chlorothiophenol (HXTPh), in whose molecule the -OH- and -SH-groups are in the ortho-position, was synthesized as a new analytical reagent. When Cr(VI) forms complexes, Cr(III) is reduced by the reagent itself. In a single extraction with chloroform as MLC, 97.4-98.9% of Cr(III) ions are extracted. The distribution coefficient corresponds to the interval $\lg CD=1.88-2.56$. The pH of the aqueous phase is 0.2-7.3 and 2.2-5.3 for the formation and maximum extraction of chromium MLC, respectively. On complexation, Cr(III) maximally absorbs light at 437-528 nm with HXTPH and hydrophobic amines. The molar coefficient of light absorption is (3.4-3.9) $\cdot 10^9$. The inhibitory effect of foreign ions was researched and new efficient photometric methods of HXTPH extraction were developed and applied for their determination in drinking and ground waters.

References:

1. О.А.Амельянчик, О.А.Большева, Т.Н. Гомонова, Н.Ф. Дурынина Е.П. Егоров, В.С. Егорова, Е.В.Едемская, Н.Л.Карпова, Е.А. Минеев В.Г. Прижукова, В.Г.Сычев, Практикум по агрохимии, Учебное пособие – 2-ое издание, Москва, "Издательство МГУ", 2001, 688 с.
2. Ф. Умланд, А. Янсен, Д. Тириг, Г. Вюнш, Комплексные соединения в аналитической химии, Теория и практика применения. Москва: - Мир, 1975, 531 с.
3. Najih, H.Sh. Spectrophotometric Determination of Chromium Using Indigo Carmine -Application in Various Samples / H.Sh. Najih, A.M. Hind // Baghdad Science Journal, -Iraq: Baghdad, - 2016, -vol.13, № 3, -p.556-568.
4. Suryati, L. Development of spectrophotometric method for determination of chromium species using hypochlorite agent based on the formation of Cr(VI)-diphenylcarbazide complex / L.Suryati, H. Sulistyarti, A.Atikah//The Journal of Pure and Applied Chemistry, Malang, - 2015, -vol. 4, №. 1, p.34-41
5. Hosseini, M.S. Cr(III)/Cr(VI) speciation determination of chromium in water samples by luminescence quenching of quercetin / M.S. Hosseini, F. Belador //Journal Hazard Materials, -2009, -vol.165, №1-3, -p.1062-1067.
6. Aliyev, S.G. Complex formation in a liquid-liquid extraction system containing nickel (II), 2-hydroxy-5-nitro thio phenol and hydrophobic amines / S.G. Aliyev, Z.G. Askerova, Y.C. Gasimova [et al.] // International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering & Technology, -India, -2018, -vol. 5, № 2, -p.54 -64.
7. Вердизаде, Н.А. Экстракционно-фотометрическое определение титана (IV) гидроксигалогенпроизводными тиофенола и аминофенолами / Н.А.Вердизаде, А.З.Залов, У.Б.Абаскулиева // Известия высших учебных заведений. Серия: Химия и химическая технология, -Москва: -2012, т.55, № 10, -с. 23-29.
8. Aranda, P.R. Determination of trace chromium(VI) in drinking water using x-ray fluorescence spectrometry after solid-phase extraction / P.R. Aranda, S. Moyano, Martinez L.D. [et al.] //Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry, -2010, -vol. 398, №2, -p.1043-1048.